

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Brief summary of the workshop on

TRANSFERS AND FINANCIAL ASSISTANCE TO URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPALITIES

Date: 14th February 2020

Venue: Faculty of Law of the UAM

Expert Guest Participants:

- Mr. Juan Bravo, executive adviser for the Ministry of Regional Policy (Ministerio de Política Territorial).
- Mr. Juan Echániz, coordinator of the Provincial Council of Barcelona (Diputación de Barcelona).
- Ms. Carmen Lucas, General Secretary of the Provincial Council of Valladolid (Diputación de Valladolid).
- Ms. Dolores Hernández, Chief of the Department for Local Assistance of the Provincial Council of Valladolid (Diputación de Valladolid).
- Mr. Tomás de la Quadra-Salcedo, General Director for Local Governments at the Ministry of Regional Policy.
- Mr. Gabriel Hurtado, Deputy Director for Local Governments Financing at the Ministry of Finance (Ministerio de Hacienda).

Core issue for discussion:

- The “relevant practice” of WP-2 (Finance arrangements) turns around the role of the state or regional *unconditional transfers* to municipalities. These transfers account in average for a 34% of all municipal revenues. Main issues for the discussion were:

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

- How these transfers are *distributed* and to what extent they *favor* large cities and hurt villages and small cities.
- To what extent the hypothetical deficit of State and regional transfers to small municipalities are compensated through the direct assistance and investments of the provincial councils (diputaciones provinciales)

Main outcomes:

- The following conclusions can be drawn from recent empirical studies:
 - Cities with a population of over 500,000 *are relatively over-financed*, when compared with smaller cities. Moreover, unconditional transfers play an important role to that output. It is due to the so-called *statu quo* clause, according to which every piece of legislation aimed at reforming the local financing system since 1988 has at least preserved the previous financial status of all municipalities.
 - There are *enormous —and unjustified— differences regarding per capita* financing by means of state unconditional transfers (e.g., the municipality of Barcelona receives 619 euros per inhabitant, while the municipality of Almeria receives 216).
 - The current system pays little regard to *population changes*.

- Regarding the financing role to be played by the *provincial councils*, we have identified two general patterns:
 - Some provincial councils (e.g. Valladolid) are exclusively intended to support small municipalities (below 20,000 inhabitants). It may rebalance the financial situation in favor of small municipalities. This is still a hypothesis, since there is no empirical evidence to support that argument.
 - Other provincial councils (e.g. Barcelona) assist or invest resources in both small and big municipalities. This may have an adverse effect on the horizontal equalization among municipalities. Again, no empirical evidence is available.

- Moreover, to perform an accurate analysis of the role played by the provincial councils, it is important to consider not only the monetary transfers but also the *benefits in kind* granted to the municipalities. For instance, public libraries in the municipalities of the province of Barcelona (mainly in the small ones) are directly managed by the provincial council.

- *Infrastructure policies* do not always have a positive impact to keep people in rural areas. For instance, high-speed trains may lead to the depopulation of small cities, since workers can commute every day.
- To sum up, it is controversial to what extent the local governments financing system plays a relevant role in the urban-rural interplay.